

Local Observables for the Renormalized Mass in the Quartic Scalar Lattice Quantum Field Theory

I: Without External Sources

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Abstract

We present and explore a set of observables that can be used to determine the renormalized mass parameter of the quantum field theory of a scalar field with a single real component and a quartic potential term in the action. The observable that is normally used for this is the momentum-space propagator. The observables presented here are local observables defined at single geometrical elements of the lattice, such as links and diagonals of plaquettes, defined therefore in position space rather than momentum space. This eliminates the need for the calculation of the Fourier transforms of the fields, which may be numerically advantageous under certain circumstances.

The quantum field theory examined here is important because it is part of the scalar sector of the standard model of particle physics. The single scalar field left over after spontaneous symmetry breaking has been implemented in that model is known as the Higgs field, which is described by this theory. This theory is known to be trivial, in the sense that, although its ensemble is not Gaussian, in the continuum limit all its expectation values are identical to those of a Gaussian theory with appropriately chosen parameters. The definition of the local observables will make use of this fact, since their expressions are derived from the Gaussian ensemble of a free theory.

We measure the dimensionless renormalized mass parameter of the quartic scalar field theory in a few different ways, in the case in which there are no external sources present, in four spacetime dimensions, on relatively small lattices. One of these measurements has a global character over the whole lattice, since it is done in momentum space. The other measurements are done in position space and have a local character, being valid on single lattice links or single diagonals of plaquettes. We present here numerical results with high-quality statistics, that show that these local observables generate results for the renormalized mass parameter that are essentially identical to those obtained from the momentum-space observable, even on small lattices.

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1 Introduction

In this paper we will examine some aspects of a well-known scalar quantum field theory known as the $\lambda\varphi^4$ polynomial scalar theory. This is a quartic theory of a single-component scalar field that has great fundamental importance due to the fact that it plays a vital role in the structure of the so-called standard model of particle physics. The scalar sector of that standard model contains a scalar field theory, for a doublet of complex scalar fields, that is essential to implement the process of spontaneous symmetry breaking which is at the very core of the structure of that model. Once the process of symmetry breaking has been completed, a single real scalar field component is left over, with its dynamics given by an action that contains a quartic term. This remaining uncharged massive scalar field is known as the Higgs field.

We will examine the question of the measurement of the renormalized mass m_R of this single-component scalar field. By construction this theory displays the phenomenon of spontaneous symmetry breaking. It is also known to be trivial [1–6], in the sense that, although its ensemble is not Gaussian, in the continuum limit all its expectation values are identical to those of a corresponding Gaussian theory, with appropriately chosen parameters. This also implies that in the continuum limit this theory reduces to a theory of free, non-interacting particles. Consequently there are only two relevant fundamental physical quantities to be calculated in this theory, the vacuum expectation value v_R of the field φ , and the renormalized mass parameter α_R associated with the corresponding particles.

We will not discuss the issue of triviality in this paper, since its existence has already been established beyond any doubt [5, 6]. Instead, we will assume its existence and use it in order to construct certain observables. In this paper we will present a set of local observables that can be used to determine the renormalized mass. The definition of these observables holds for any scalar field theory, in any spacetime dimension $d \geq 3$, but we will focus mostly on the $\lambda\varphi^4$ theory in four-dimensional spacetime. The usual way to measure this parameter is through the use of the two-point function in momentum space, that is, the momentum-space propagator. The observables to be presented here are local observables defined in position space rather than momentum space. They are local in the sense that they are associated with single geometrical elements of the lattice, such as links and diagonals of plaquettes, which are the natural geometrical elements with which to associate correlations between the two sites at either end of each such element.

The use of these observables instead of the momentum-space propagator eliminates the need for the calculation of the Fourier transforms of the fields, which may be numerically advantageous for a few reasons. First, the repeated calculation of Fourier transforms is a rather expensive numerical operation. Second, if it is implemented in the most numerically efficient way possible, it involves a extremely large real matrix, which can lead to memory exhaustion problems. In addition to this, in some circumstances, such as the presence of non-homogeneous external sources, there may be conceptual problems in using measurements in momentum space, since these are global over the whole lattice and thus completely ignore this non-homogeneity. In this paper the scalar field theory will be defined in a mathematically precise fashion using a discrete representation on what is known as an Euclidean lattice. The continuum theory in Euclidean space is to be obtained as a limit from this discrete Euclidean construction, after which a Wick rotation is to be executed, leading to the corresponding continuum theory in Minkowski spacetime.

This paper is organized as follows: in Section 2 we define the quartic scalar theory; in Section 3 we describe the basic structural properties of that theory; in Section 4 we discuss the momentum-space observable for the renormalized mass parameter; in Section 5 we in-

roduce the local observables for the renormalized mass parameter; in Section 6 we describe the numerical methods and the computer programs used in the numerical exploration; in Section 7 we present the numerical results; and in Section 8 we present our conclusions.

2 Definition of the Theory

Here we will give the definition of the theory, in order to establish the notation and the basic mathematical facts about it. If we are to make any meaningful and precise statements about any theory, it is imperative that we start from a precise mathematical definition of that theory. We will use as the very definition of any given quantum field theory its realization on a discrete Euclidean lattice. In this constructive definition a discrete version of the theory is set up on finite lattices in Euclidean space, in a way which is valid for arbitrarily large values of the size of the lattice. The corresponding theory in the Minkowski continuum is obtained when we make the lattice infinitely large and its mesh infinitely fine, and execute a Wick rotation from the resulting Euclidean space to the corresponding Minkowski spacetime.

In order to define the theory and establish the notation, we will consider a discrete Cartesian lattice with N sites in each one of d spacetime directions, hence with a total of N^d sites and dN^d links between neighboring sites. Roughly speaking, the lattice is a discrete representation of spacetime. If the components of the d -vector \vec{n} are the d discrete integer coordinates of the lattice sites in d dimensions, then the lattice field $\varphi = \varphi(\vec{n})$ is defined as a real function of these discrete coordinates, where

$$\vec{n} = (n_1, \dots, n_d), \quad (1)$$

$$n_\mu = 1, \dots, N, \quad (2)$$

$$\mu = 1, \dots, d, \quad (3)$$

where $\varphi(\vec{n})$ is a single-component real scalar field, which on the lattice formalism is always a dimensionless quantity. The relevant geometrical elements of the lattice itself are its sites \vec{n} , its links l_μ between neighboring sites along the Cartesian direction μ , and its plaquettes. By definition the lattice consists of N^d sites, and of dN^d links between neighboring sites. We assume that periodic boundary conditions are used on the lattice, meaning that along any given direction μ the site $n_\mu = N + 1$ is identified with the site $n_\mu = 1$, and that the site $n_\mu = 0$ is identified with the site $n_\mu = N$. Given a site \vec{n} and a direction μ , the link l_μ simply connects the site \vec{n} to its neighboring site $\vec{n} + 1_\mu$ in that direction, and is the natural locus for the finite difference of the two values of the field at either site. Here 1_μ represents the increment in the μ coordinate from the site \vec{n} to its next neighbor in the positive direction μ , going from a given value of n_μ to the value $n_\mu + 1$.

The plaquettes are two-dimensional objects constructed as follows. One starts at a given site \vec{n} and considers two positive directions departing from it, say μ and ν . The plaquette is the square generated by the two links l_μ and l_ν . Since there are $d!/2!(d-2)!$ ways to choose the two positive directions from a given site, it is clear that there are $d(d-1)N^d/2$ plaquettes in an N -lattice in d dimensions. If we consider the diagonals of plaquettes, since there are two diagonals per plaquette, it is clear that the total number of such diagonals on the N -lattice in d dimensions is given by $d(d-1)N^d$. Note that these diagonals are necessary to help upgrade the Cartesian lattice to a simplicial complex, over which a definite metric geometry can be unequivocally defined. Therefore it is important to be able to determine the lengths of these diagonals, as well as the lengths of the links.

The Euclidean action functional defining the scalar field theory on the lattice is given in this d -dimensional discrete position space by

$$S_N[\varphi] = \sum_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mu=1}^d [\Delta_\mu \varphi(\vec{n})]^2 + \frac{\alpha}{2} \varphi^2(\vec{n}) + \frac{\lambda}{4} \varphi^4(\vec{n}) \right\}, \quad (4)$$

where the sum over \vec{n} runs over all N^d lattice sites, so that it can be expressed as a d -dimensional multiple sum,

$$\sum_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} \equiv \sum_{n_1=1}^N \cdots \sum_{n_d=1}^N, \quad (5)$$

and where the lattice squared mass parameter α is a dimensionless real parameter, while the lattice coupling constant λ is a dimensionless positive real parameter. The operator Δ_μ represents the finite difference of the fields across the lattice link starting at the site \vec{n} in the positive direction μ . Note that α can be negative so long as λ is strictly positive, thus ensuring the energetic stability of the theory or, in quantum terminology, the existence of its ground state. These stability constraints will be discussed in more detail in Section 3. If λ is zero then α has to be positive, and in this case our theory reduces to the free quantum field theory of the single real scalar field $\varphi(\vec{n})$. If we introduce a lattice spacing a with physical dimensions of length it is not difficult to show that for $\alpha \geq 0$ the expression shown in Equation (4) tends to the usual classical expression for the action of this theory in the continuum limit, within a finite cubic box in d dimensions,

$$S[\phi] = \int_V d^d x \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mu=1}^d [\partial_\mu \phi(\vec{x})]^2 + \frac{m^2}{2} \phi^2(\vec{x}) + \frac{\Lambda}{4} \phi^4(\vec{x}) \right\}, \quad (6)$$

where we introduced, still on finite lattices, the dimensionfull quantities given by the squared mass $m^2 = \alpha/a^2$, the dimensionfull coupling constant $\Lambda = a^{d-4}\lambda$, and the dimensionfull field $\phi(\vec{x}) = \varphi(\vec{n})/a^{(d-2)/2}$, where $\vec{x} = a\vec{n}$ are now dimensionfull coordinates on the lattice, so that the minimum possible variation of a coordinate is $dx^\mu = a$, the d -dimensional integration element is $d^d x = a^d$, the lattice length is $L = Na$ and the lattice volume is $V = L^d$. After that we take the continuum limit, in which $N \rightarrow \infty$ and $a \rightarrow 0$, in such a way that the lattice length $L = Na$ remains constant, under some auxiliary conditions involving the dimensionless parameters α and λ of the theory, meant at keeping the renormalized mass m_R finite in the limit.

The observable quantities of the quantum field theory are the average values of functionals of the field on the statistical distribution of field configurations, also known as an ensemble, defined by the exponential of minus the action. These are called expectation values and, given an arbitrary observable $\mathcal{O}[\varphi]$, which in general is some functional of the field, its expectation value is defined as the ratio of multiple integrals

$$\langle \mathcal{O} \rangle_N = \frac{\int [d\varphi]_N e^{-S_N[\varphi]} \mathcal{O}[\varphi]}{\int [d\varphi]_N e^{-S_N[\varphi]}}, \quad (7)$$

where the integrals indicated are functional integrals, that is, sums over the set of all possible field configurations $\varphi(\vec{n})$ on the lattice. On a finite N -lattice in d dimensions they can be written as multiple integrals in a real space of dimension N^d , with the measure

$$[d\varphi]_N = \prod_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} d\varphi(\vec{n}), \quad (8)$$

where the product over \vec{n} runs over all N^d lattice sites, so that it can be expressed as a d -dimensional multiple product,

$$\prod_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} \equiv \prod_{n_1=1}^N \dots \prod_{n_d=1}^N. \quad (9)$$

The integrals over $\varphi(\vec{n})$ at each site \vec{n} , shown in Equation (7), are taken from $\varphi(\vec{n}) \rightarrow -\infty$ to $\varphi(\vec{n}) \rightarrow \infty$. In the $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit the integrals in Equation (7) become infinite-dimensional integrals, also known as functional integrals in the continuum.

Some of the most important expectation values of the theory are defined in momentum space, so let us introduce the representation of the theory in that space. The field $\varphi(\vec{n})$, defined at first in position space, can also be represented in momentum space, in the case of the use of periodic boundary conditions on the lattice, by its Fourier components $\tilde{\varphi}$, also known as the coefficients of the expansion of the field in lattice modes. If $\vec{\kappa}$ are the discrete integer momentum coordinates of these modes on the conjugate lattice in momentum space, then the Fourier components $\tilde{\varphi} = \tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa})$ are defined as complex functions of these modes, where

$$\vec{\kappa} = (\kappa_1, \dots, \kappa_d), \quad (10)$$

$$\kappa_\mu = \kappa_{\min}, \dots, \kappa_{\max}, \quad (11)$$

$$\mu = 1, \dots, d, \quad (12)$$

and where the extremes of the discrete momentum-space coordinates κ_μ are given by

$$\kappa_{\min} = \begin{cases} -\frac{N-1}{2} & \text{for odd } N, \\ -\frac{N}{2} + 1 & \text{for even } N, \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

$$\kappa_{\max} = \begin{cases} \frac{N-1}{2} & \text{for odd } N, \\ \frac{N}{2} & \text{for even } N. \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

The conjugate lattice has the same geometrical structure of the original lattice, being Cartesian with N points along each one of d independent directions, but which represent now modes rather than sites. In this paper we will use only even values of N , because for algorithmic reasons this is the most important case for the numerical simulations, due to the use of periodic boundary conditions. The finite Fourier transformation and its inverse, between these two representations of the field, are exact relations given by

$$\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa}) = \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} e^{i\frac{2\pi}{N}\vec{\kappa}\cdot\vec{n}} \varphi(\vec{n}), \quad (15)$$

$$\varphi(\vec{n}) = \sum_{\vec{\kappa}}^{N^d} e^{-i\frac{2\pi}{N}\vec{\kappa}\cdot\vec{n}} \tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa}), \quad (16)$$

where the sum over $\vec{\kappa}$ runs over all N^d lattice modes, so that it can be expressed as a d -dimensional multiple sum,

$$\sum_{\vec{\kappa}}^{N^d} \equiv \sum_{\kappa_1=\kappa_{\min}}^{\kappa_{\max}} \cdots \sum_{\kappa_d=\kappa_{\min}}^{\kappa_{\max}}, \quad (17)$$

and where the set of complex exponentials shown in these transformation formulas constitutes a complete and orthogonal basis for the representation of arbitrary functions on the lattice, known as the Fourier basis. The first expression, in Equation (15) above, defines the Fourier components of the field, and the second expression, in Equation (16) above, can be interpreted as the decomposition of the field in lattice modes. Note that, since $\varphi(\vec{n})$ is real, from Equation (15) it follows that the Fourier components satisfy the constraints

$$\tilde{\varphi}^*(\vec{\kappa}) = \tilde{\varphi}(-\vec{\kappa}). \quad (18)$$

Modes $\vec{\kappa}$ with all components equal to either 0 or $N/2$ are real modes, since in these cases the complex exponential functions representing the modes are real functions, and hence the Fourier components are also real. For even N there are 2^d real modes, which are at the vertices of a d -dimensional cube within the conjugate lattice in momentum space, of extent $N/2$ in each direction, going from the zero mode $(0, \dots, 0)$ to the maximal mode $(N/2, \dots, N/2)$. For odd N there is a single real mode, the zero mode $\vec{\kappa} = \vec{0}$. Note that from Equation (15) it follows that the coefficient of the zero mode $\tilde{\varphi}_0 = \tilde{\varphi}(\vec{0})$ is a full-lattice block variable, that is, the average of the field over the whole lattice,

$$\tilde{\varphi}_0 = \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} \varphi(\vec{n}). \quad (19)$$

This real quantity will be instrumental in the determination of the state of symmetry breaking of the quartic polynomial theory. The observable $\langle \tilde{\varphi}_0^2 \rangle$ or, more precisely, the corresponding observable formed by the difference of expectation values

$$\sigma_0^2 = \langle \tilde{\varphi}_0^2 \rangle - \langle \tilde{\varphi}_0 \rangle^2, \quad (20)$$

which is the squared width of the distribution of values of $\tilde{\varphi}_0$, can be used as an order parameter for the two phases of the theory, since for large N it tends to zero in the symmetric phase, and remains different from zero in the broken-symmetric phase. Although the symmetry breaking mechanism only becomes exact in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit, this observable can be used to determine approximately the location of the phase transition in the (α, λ) parameter plane, even on finite lattices. It is noteworthy that the dimensionless renormalized mass parameter α_R , to be discussed in what follows, can also be used for this purpose. On finite lattices the direction of symmetry breaking tends to drift (in our case here to flip sign), in such a way that the expectation value $\langle \tilde{\varphi}_0 \rangle$ is averaged out to zero during the drift. This drift only ceases completely in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit.

In the same way, due to this drift and consequent averaging out, the expectation value $v_R = \langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \rangle$ of the field, which in the continuum limit is different from zero only in the broken-symmetric phase, is always zero on finite lattices, in either phase, and hence cannot be used as the order parameter. In practical terms the actual value of the expectation value v_R is not available for measurement on the lattices that we use here. In order to have $v_R \neq 0$ on finite lattices it is necessary to break the symmetry by hand, by either using fixed boundary conditions oriented in a predetermined way, or including in the theory an

external source $j(\vec{n})$ with a predetermined orientation, which can be done by adding the term $-j(\vec{n})\varphi(\vec{n})$ to the summand of the action shown in Equation (4). Note that the introduction of such an external source would cause $v_R(\vec{n})$ to depend on position, unless $j(\vec{n})$ was actually constant over the lattice.

The action of the $\lambda\varphi^4$ theory shown in Equation (4) can be written in terms of $\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa})$, as $S_N[\tilde{\varphi}]$, but its form in this representation is neither simple nor particularly useful. By transforming the fields to momentum space we may write the expectation value, in terms of the Fourier transforms of the fields, as

$$\langle \mathcal{O} \rangle_N = \frac{\int [d\tilde{\varphi}]_N e^{-S_N[\tilde{\varphi}]} \mathcal{O}[\tilde{\varphi}]}{\int [d\tilde{\varphi}]_N e^{-S_N[\tilde{\varphi}]}} \quad (21)$$

where the measure is now given symbolically by

$$[d\tilde{\varphi}]_N = \prod_{\vec{\kappa}}^{N^d} d\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa}), \quad (22)$$

where for a more precise description $d\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa})$ should be replaced by $d\Re[\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa})]d\Im[\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa})]$, and where the values of $\vec{\kappa}$ and the real and imaginary parts of $\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa})$ have to be selected so as to neither under-count nor over-count the N^d independent field variables, that is, they must take into account the constraints given in Equation (18) and the fact that some modes are real and thus have no imaginary parts. The most fundamental expectation value in the theory is that of the two-point function in momentum space, also known as the propagator, which is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\langle |\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa})|^2 \right\rangle_N - \left| \langle \tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa}) \rangle_N \right|^2 \\ &= \frac{\int [d\tilde{\varphi}]_N e^{-S_N[\tilde{\varphi}]} |\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa})|^2}{\int [d\tilde{\varphi}]_N e^{-S_N[\tilde{\varphi}]}} - \left| \frac{\int [d\tilde{\varphi}]_N e^{-S_N[\tilde{\varphi}]} \tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa})}{\int [d\tilde{\varphi}]_N e^{-S_N[\tilde{\varphi}]}} \right|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

This observable defines the important physical quantity that is the renormalized dimensionless squared mass parameter α_R of the theory. This parameter is related to the correlation length of the field on the lattice. In terms of the dimensionfull renormalized mass m_R it is given by $\alpha_R = m_R^2 a^2$, so that finite values of m_R in the $N \rightarrow \infty$, $a \rightarrow 0$ continuum limit correspond to $\alpha_R \rightarrow 0$. This condition implies that all continuum limits must converge to the critical curve of the theory in the (α, λ) parameter plane, as will be discussed in detail in Section 3. The observable parameter $\sqrt{\alpha_R}$ can be defined as the position of the single pole of this momentum-space two-point function, when it is written in the Minkowski spacetime by means of a Wick rotation. The ratios of high-dimensional integrals that define the expectation values can be calculated efficiently and with good precision by stochastic methods known as Monte Carlo simulations, or stochastic simulations. Since there are no known exact solutions of these non-linear theories, we will have to use these numerical methods in order to calculate physical quantities.

3 Fundamental Properties

Here we will describe the main structural properties of the theory. Let us start by examining the stability constraints on the theory, that follow from its definition. Examining the action

$S_N[\varphi]$ given in Equation (4) we now observe that, for any finite value of N , in order for the integrals over each degree of freedom $\varphi(\vec{n})$ to exist and be finite, and hence for the Euclidean ensemble defined in Equations (7) and (21) above to be well-defined, we need to have one of the following two conditions hold: either $\lambda > 0$ with any real value of α , or $\lambda = 0$ with $\alpha > 0$. This requirement corresponds to the condition that $S_N[\varphi]$ must have a lower bound.

In any case, the condition $\lambda < 0$ implies that the integrals do not exist, because in this case $S_N[\varphi]$ has no lower bound, as one can see by considering arbitrarily large constant field configurations, and therefore the factor $\exp(-S_N[\varphi])$ in the integrands diverges very fast to $+\infty$ at the two ends of the integration interval, that is, both for $\varphi(\vec{n}) \rightarrow -\infty$ and for $\varphi(\vec{n}) \rightarrow \infty$, so that the integrals do not exist. This is true on each finite N -lattice, and therefore it is also true in any $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit. In terms of the Minkowski theory, this condition is translated as the fact that the Hamiltonian of the theory has no lower bound, and that therefore there is no ground state of the quantum theory. Note that this argument implies that for $\lambda < 0$ the quantum theory fails to exist for any and all finite values of N , so that this limitation on the possible values of λ is not only a consequence of the $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit. If the limitation is violated, then the theory fails to exist on each and every one of the finite- N lattices, all the way to the $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit.

We must now describe the phenomenology of the lattice theory, in particular with respect to the mechanism of the continuum limit and to the mechanism of symmetry breaking, which are related to each other. Here we must point out that the actions shown in Equations (4) and (6) are invariant by an $O(1)$ discrete global reflection symmetry, in which we flip the signs of the fields. Both mechanisms are also closely related to the critical behavior of the lattice theory in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit, if we interpret it as a statistical model of a set of random variables $\varphi(\vec{n})$. The other crucially important property of the theory is that of the so-called triviality, which was already mentioned. The critical diagram of the $\lambda\varphi^4$ theory can be found in Figure 1. This is a qualitative diagram in the space of the parameters of the theory, in our case here the (α, λ) parameter plane. The qualitative aspects of the diagram are the same for any dimension $d \geq 3$, including the important case $d = 4$. Some aspects of the diagram are over-emphasized for visualization purposes. The alternative parameters r and θ , that will be used instead of α and λ in the numerical work, are defined to be such that

$$\alpha = -r \cos(\theta), \tag{24}$$

$$\lambda = r \sin(\theta). \tag{25}$$

The critical behavior of the theory can be well illustrated by varying θ at constant r . The diagram consists of three regions. In the region below the α axis the theory does not exist at all, since in this region, where $\lambda < 0$, it has no stable ground state, given that $S_N[\varphi]$ has no lower bound there. We call that one the unstable or forbidden region. The strictly negative part of the α axis is part of this region, since in this negative semi-axis we have $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha < 0$, and once more the theory has no stable ground state. Above the α axis there are two distinct regions separated by a critical curve. To the right of the critical curve we have the symmetric phase, and to its left we have the broken-symmetric phase. The critical curve starts at the Gaussian critical point, which is the origin of the (α, λ) plane, and proceeds more or less linearly to infinity with $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$ and $\alpha \rightarrow -\infty$. At the arc at infinity in this direction the theory reduces to the Ising model in d dimensions, with its parameter associated to θ , in the interval $(0, \pi/2)$. In this limit the action shown in Equation (4) can be reduced to that of the Ising model, given by $-\beta \sum_{\text{links}} \psi_{\oplus} \psi_{\ominus}$, where $\psi = \pm 1$ and $\beta = \cot(\theta)$.

Figure 1: The critical diagram of the $\lambda\varphi^4$ theory, showing the unstable region, the symmetric region, the broken-symmetric region and the critical curve separating these last two. Flows representing possible continuum limits, from each one of the two phases of the theory, are also shown. For simplicity, the parameters (r, θ) seen here will be used instead of (α, λ) in the simulations.

The critical curve divides the upper half of the diagram in two regions, which constitute the two phases of the theory, when interpreted as a statistical model. The transition from one phase to the other is a second-order phase transitions, in which the order parameter varies continuously across the critical curve in the $N \rightarrow \infty$, $a \rightarrow 0$ continuum limit. At the critical curve we have that $\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda) \rightarrow 0$ when we take the $N \rightarrow \infty$, $a \rightarrow 0$ continuum limit. The symmetric phase is characterized by having $v_R \rightarrow 0$ in the continuum limit, while in the broken-symmetric phase we have $v_R \neq 0$ when we take the continuum limit, but the behavior of v_R in this limit is quite discontinuous, since due to the drift on finite lattices it is zero all over the parameter plane, for any finite value of N .

The continuum limits can be represented by paths in this diagram, which we call flows. All limits of physical interest, which must result in a finite renormalized mass m_R , converge to some point on the critical curve, where $\alpha_R \rightarrow 0$ in the continuum limit. The ensemble of the theory is Gaussian in the positive half-axis $\alpha \geq 0$, $\lambda = 0$, where we have the free theory, and the continuum limits of this free theory flow to the left along this half-axis, converging to the Gaussian critical point $\alpha = 0$, $\lambda = 0$, where the critical curve begins. In the neighborhood of the Gaussian critical point the critical curve differs very little from a straight line. This is also true asymptotically, for very large r .

4 Momentum Observables

The triviality of the theory means that in the continuum limit it is equivalent to the Gaussian theory given, in its most general possible form, by

$$S_E[\varphi] = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{\vec{n}} \frac{1}{R} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mu=1}^d [\Delta_\mu \varphi(\vec{x})]^2 + \frac{\alpha_R}{2} \varphi^2(\vec{x}) - \alpha_R v_R \varphi(\vec{x}) \right\}, \quad (26)$$

where α_R is the renormalized version of the parameter α , v_R is the vacuum expectation value of $\varphi(\vec{x})$, and R is a possible field renormalization factor, that appears as the residue in the form of the momentum-space propagator. Given that the theory becomes Gaussian in the continuum limit, it is to be expected that the central observable of the $\lambda\varphi^4$ theory in momentum space, the two-point function or the momentum-space propagator, has the form implied by the free theory in the continuum limit. It is to be expected that on finite lattices this form is just an approximation, that becomes exact in the continuum limit. We therefore assume that the propagator is given on finite lattices by

$$\left\langle |\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k})|^2 \right\rangle_N - \left| \langle \tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k}) \rangle_N \right|^2 = \frac{R(\alpha, \lambda)}{N^d [\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda)]}, \quad (27)$$

where the residue $R(\alpha, \lambda)$ and the renormalized square mass parameter $\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda)$ are functions of the free parameters of the theory as indicated, and where the eigenvalues of the discrete Laplacian are given by $-\rho^2(\vec{k})$, where

$$\rho^2(\vec{k}) = \sum_{\mu=1}^d \rho_\mu^2(\vec{k}), \quad (28)$$

$$\rho_\mu(\vec{k}) = 2 \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{N} \kappa_\mu\right). \quad (29)$$

In fact the numerical experience, as we will show in this paper, indicates that this form of the momentum-space propagator works very well even on very small lattices, and with very good precision, for all momentum-space modes except for the zero mode. This is due to the phenomenon of spontaneous symmetry breaking that occurs in this theory, which requires us to treat the zero mode in a separate way.

Note that in Equation (27) we may omit the subtraction of the propagator, because in our circumstances here we have that $\langle \varphi(\vec{x}) \rangle_N = 0$ due to the random drift of the direction of symmetry breaking, which implies that we also have $\langle \tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k}) \rangle_N = 0$. The eigenvalues of the discrete Laplacian are related to the dimensionfull linear momentum variable p_μ by

$$\rho_\mu(\vec{k}) = p_\mu(\vec{k})a. \quad (30)$$

In the $N \rightarrow \infty$, $a \rightarrow 0$ continuum limit at constant L this reduces to the usual form of the linear momentum within a box of size L , namely $p_\mu(\vec{k}) = 2\pi\kappa_\mu/L$. By measuring numerically the propagator on the left-hand side of Equation (27), for all \vec{k} except for the zero mode, we are able to obtain the values of R and α_R , if we simply fit the numerical results to the formula in the right-hand side of Equation (27). The accuracy of the fit will give us information about the quality of the representation of the propagator by the expression shown in the right-hand side of Equation (27). In principle this fit includes the zero mode, but we will explicitly avoid including the zero mode in the fit. We do this because the zero mode is sensitive to the process of symmetry breaking that leads to the phase transition, and is changed by the phase transition when one passes from the symmetric phase to the

broken-symmetric phase. Since the Fourier modes are all orthogonal to one another, all other modes are insensitive to the phase transition and to the behavior of the zero mode. The remaining modes are more than enough to determine R and α_R very well, even on very small lattices.

Note that, since it involves all the modes on the lattice, this kind of measurement of α_R is global to the whole lattice, and not local to any particular geometrical element of it. Note also that it results from this type of fit that $R(\alpha, \lambda)$ is a positive real constant independent of $\rho^2(\vec{k})$, for all α and all λ , even if it is not always the value of 1, which is the exact result of the free theory with its Gaussian ensemble. The existence of a constant value of R different from 1 means only that the field of the related Gaussian model has to be rescaled by \sqrt{R} , and does not spoil the fact that the action of that related model is quadratic, and therefore that the related model is Gaussian. One can obtain the exact action of the free theory in terms of a rescaled field $\varphi' = \varphi/\sqrt{R}$. This simply means that the non-linear theory under scrutiny here undergoes a finite field renormalization. In Section 5 we will present some local observables that will also allow us to measure α_R .

5 Local Observables

Once again we will use here the triviality property of the theory. We consider a Gaussian theory in which the renormalized parameter α_R of the non-linear theory plays the role of the parameter α , and the subtracted field $\varphi(\vec{n}) - v_R$ plays the role of the free field. Here we will develop a set of local observables that depend on the value of the dimensionless renormalized mass parameter α_R . We start in the free theory, where these observables can be calculated exactly on each finite lattice, by analytic means. In the free theory, in which we make $\lambda = 0$ and use the renormalized value α_R of the $\lambda\varphi^4$ theory for the parameter α , and for which we have the complete exact solution of the theory and can therefore calculate any required quantities, it is not difficult to show that the exact solution for the two-point function in momentum space is given by

$$\left\langle |\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k})|^2 \right\rangle_N - \left| \langle \tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k}) \rangle_N \right|^2 = \frac{1}{N^d [\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R]}, \quad (31)$$

by simple Gaussian integration. It is also not difficult to show that from this result it follows that the exact solution for the two-point function in position space is given by

$$\left\langle \varphi(\vec{n}') \varphi(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N - \left\langle \varphi(\vec{n}') \right\rangle_N \left\langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N = \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k}} \frac{\cos\left[\frac{2\pi}{N} \vec{k} \cdot (\vec{n}' - \vec{n})\right]}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R}. \quad (32)$$

Next, from this result we may obtain the correlations between the values of the field at two different lattice sites located close together, both across single links and across single diagonals of plaquettes, as well as the width of the local distribution of values of the field at single sites. If we make $\vec{n}' = \vec{n}$ we get at once from Equation (32)

$$\left\langle \varphi^2(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N - \left\langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N^2 = \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k}} \frac{1}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R}. \quad (33)$$

This is the width of the local distribution of values of the field at a single site \vec{n} . It is noteworthy that this quantity has a finite and non-zero value in the continuum limit, a value that does not depend on the value that m_R has in that limit, so long as that value is finite and non-zero. This is caused by the fact that $\alpha_R \rightarrow 0$ in any continuum limit that

results in a finite value for the renormalized mass m_R . Note that this observable does not really depend on the position \vec{n} . In the case of the links between two next neighbors, if we make $\vec{n}' = \vec{n} + 1_\mu$, we have from Equation (32), for the correlation over links,

$$\left\langle \varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu) \varphi(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N - \left\langle \varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu) \right\rangle_N \left\langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N = \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k}} \frac{\cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{N} \kappa_\mu\right)}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R}. \quad (34)$$

Note that again this observable does not depend on the position \vec{n} . In the case of the diagonals of plaquettes, if we make $\vec{n}' = \vec{n} + 1_\mu \pm 1_\nu$ we have from Equation (32), for the correlation over plaquette diagonals,

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu \pm 1_\nu) \varphi(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N - \left\langle \varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu \pm 1_\nu) \right\rangle_N \left\langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N \\ = \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k}} \frac{\cos\left[\frac{2\pi}{N}(\kappa_\mu \pm \kappa_\nu)\right]}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R}. \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

Note that once more this observable does not depend on the position \vec{n} . It is also very simple to generalize these expressions to diagonals of higher-dimensional elementary lattice objects, such as three-dimensional cells, in the spacetime dimensions d in which they exist.

Other important and useful observables can be constructed using the finite differences of the fields at the two ends of links or plaquette diagonals. While these finite differences can have either positive or negative values, and due to the symmetries of the theory the corresponding expectation values average out to zero, their squares have non-zero averages, can easily be measured, and hence can also be used to determine the renormalized mass parameter α_R . By expanding the squares of the differences these observables can be written in terms of those shown in Equations (33), (34) and (35), and in this way we obtain for the squared differences over links

$$\left\langle [\varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu) - \varphi(\vec{n})]^2 \right\rangle_N = \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k}} \frac{4 \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi}{N} \kappa_\mu\right)}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R}, \quad (36)$$

and for the squared differences over plaquette diagonals

$$\left\langle [\varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu \pm 1_\nu) - \varphi(\vec{n})]^2 \right\rangle_N = \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k}} \frac{4 \sin^2\left[\frac{\pi}{N}(\kappa_\mu \pm \kappa_\nu)\right]}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R}. \quad (37)$$

The results shown in Equations (33) through (37) are all exact results of the free theory, with its Gaussian ensemble. All the expressions shown in the right-hand sides of these equations are functions of α_R , so that by measuring numerically the functions on the left-hand sides, in the non-linear theory, and then solving the equations for α_R defined by the functions on the right-hand sides, we have several different ways of measuring the renormalized mass parameter α_R . The resulting equations for α_R can be solved numerically without too much difficulty. Of course, one can only expect these measurements to be exact in the $N \rightarrow \infty$, $a \rightarrow 0$ continuum limit.

In order to account for the possible necessity of field renormalization, that is, for the possibility that we have for the residue of the propagator $R(\alpha, \lambda) \neq 1$, a different but related set of observables can be used. Taking the results for the residue R obtained from the momentum-space measurements, we may use instead of Equations (33) through (37), the following five relations between the measured functions in the non-linear theory and the results of the free theory. For the squared fields at sites we have

$$\langle \varphi^2(\vec{n}) \rangle_N - \langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \rangle_N^2 = R \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{\kappa}} \frac{1}{\rho^2(\vec{\kappa}) + \alpha_R}, \quad (38)$$

for the correlation over links we have

$$\langle \varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu) \varphi(\vec{n}) \rangle_N - \langle \varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu) \rangle_N \langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \rangle_N = R \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{\kappa}} \frac{\cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{N} \kappa_\mu\right)}{\rho^2(\vec{\kappa}) + \alpha_R}, \quad (39)$$

for the correlation over plaquette diagonals we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle \varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu \pm 1_\nu) \varphi(\vec{n}) \rangle_N - \langle \varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu \pm 1_\nu) \rangle_N \langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \rangle_N \\ &= R \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{\kappa}} \frac{\cos\left[\frac{2\pi}{N}(\kappa_\mu \pm \kappa_\nu)\right]}{\rho^2(\vec{\kappa}) + \alpha_R}, \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

for the squared differences over links we have

$$\langle [\varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu) - \varphi(\vec{n})]^2 \rangle_N = R \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{\kappa}} \frac{4 \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi}{N} \kappa_\mu\right)}{\rho^2(\vec{\kappa}) + \alpha_R}, \quad (41)$$

and for the squared differences over plaquette diagonals we have

$$\langle [\varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu \pm 1_\nu) - \varphi(\vec{n})]^2 \rangle_N = R \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{\kappa}} \frac{4 \sin^2\left[\frac{\pi}{N}(\kappa_\mu \pm \kappa_\nu)\right]}{\rho^2(\vec{\kappa}) + \alpha_R}. \quad (42)$$

If we write the expectation values of the non-linear theory in the left-hand sides in terms of a renormalized field $\varphi' = \varphi/\sqrt{R}$, then the multiplicative renormalization factors \sqrt{R} of the fields cancel off, and we end up with the results of the free theory related to the renormalized field of the non-linear theory. In writing these expressions we must recall that the squared-field observables $\langle \varphi^2(\vec{n}) \rangle_N$, $\langle \varphi^2(\vec{n} + 1_\mu) \rangle_N$ and $\langle \varphi^2(\vec{n} + 1_\mu \pm 1_\nu) \rangle_N$ at single sites are all equal, since these expectation values do not really depend on the position \vec{n} .

While the result obtained from the momentum-space expression in Equation (27) is necessarily a global one, valid for the lattice as a whole, those obtained from the position-space expressions in Equations from (33) through (42) are all local, being valid for particular sites, links or plaquette diagonals, as the case may be. If we introduce into the theory a position-dependent external source $j(\vec{n})$, then all these local quantities will in fact depend on the position \vec{n} , as well as on the direction μ , and then the global momentum-space results for α_R obtained from Equation (27) lose much of their significance. Of course in such a case there is no trouble in doing the measurements in position space, since in the presence of any external source $j(\vec{n})$ the random lattice drift stops, and then the expectation values of the fields seen above become well-defined and easily measurable. This shows that the local observables for the parameter α_R are potentially very useful ones. We will use the symbol α_R for the value obtained from the propagator in momentum space, $\alpha_{R,s}$ for the value obtained from the width at sites, $\alpha_{R,l}$ for the value obtained from correlations over links, $\alpha_{R,d}$ for the value obtained from correlations over plaquette diagonals, $\alpha_{R,\Delta l}$ for the value obtained from squared differences over links, and $\alpha_{R,\Delta d}$ for the value obtained from squared differences over plaquette diagonals.

In this paper we will emphasize primarily the measurements of α_R obtained from Equations (41) and (42), since these observables are insensitive to the behavior of the zero mode

and thus to the phenomenon of spontaneous symmetry breaking that exists in the quartic scalar theories. So long as we have a constant expectation value of the field, which is expressed as a non-zero but constant coefficient of the zero mode, these observables are insensitive to the behavior of this zero mode, since if we add a non-zero vacuum expectation value to the field, this constant term would cancel off in the difference of the two fields at the two ends of the link or plaquette diagonal. Due to this these two observables will return the correct values of α_R both in the symmetric phase and in the broken-symmetric phase. The other three observables give essentially the same correct results in the symmetric phase, but are significantly distorted by the spontaneous symmetry breaking mechanism in the broken-symmetric phase.

Since in this paper we will not introduce any external sources at all, the results shown in Equations from (33) through (42) will all be independent of position. In this case we can compare them to the global result in Equations (27), as a test of these observables. In such a situation we may also, in each case, average the values obtained for the squared fields, the correlation functions and the squared difference functions, over all sites, all links or all diagonals, as the case may be, with the objective of further improving the statistical quality of these results.

6 Description of the Numerical Methods

Here we will give a general description of the numerical methods and of the computer programs used to generate the data shown in the graphs presented in Section 7. There are several programs involved, and the whole set is freely available on the Web, where it is being distributed under the GNU GPL. A compressed `tar` file with all the programs, auxiliary files and documentation can be easily and freely downloaded from Zenodo [7]. The programs have been developed and tested only of the Linux operating system, but it should not be too difficult to port them to other Unix-like operating systems. Overall there are about 7000 lines of Fortran code in a little more than 150 modules, and a few C modules for interface with the Linux system calls. The contents of the `tar` file should work right out of the box in any Linux system that has the necessary development software installed, such as the GNU Fortran compiler `gfortran`, the GNU C compiler `gcc` and the `make` utility. The programs run with standard double-precision (64-bit) real variables. The source code is extensively documented internally by comment lines, and there is a `README` file with the basic instructions for compiling and running the programs.

The stochastic simulations are worked out in two phases, in the first of which a randomly chosen initial configuration of the field is relaxed to a typical one for the set of free parameters in use, and in the second of which statistical samplings are collected. There are two main Monte Carlo programs, one called `Main_relaxer` for the relaxation phase and one called `Main_sampler` for the sampling phase. In the relaxation phase we also run a couple of feedback mechanisms in order to adjust two technical parameters, the range of the random walk in the Metropolis algorithm and the number of clusters in the Wolff cluster algorithm, in order to ensure that the acceptance rates of both the Metropolis updates and the Wolff cluster updates are kept as close as possible to 50%, in order to maximize the efficiency of the process of diffusion of the Markovian chain through the space of configurations. This works well almost always, the exception being deep in the broken-symmetric phase, where the Wolff clusters span essentially the whole lattice, so that the Wolff cluster acceptance rate approaches 100% even with the construction of only a single cluster.

There are a few additional processing phases after the statistical sampling phase is finished. The additional programs are meant to do basic statistical analysis of the results,

such as the calculation of the final averages and of their standard statistical errors, which is what the program `Main_oversaw` does, and then to do the data analysis, with a program called `Main_propres` for the results relating to the momentum-space propagator, including the fits in momentum space, and another program called `Main_lobsres` for the results relating to the local observables. In these last two phases equivalent data is consolidated, in order to improve the statistical quality of the results. In the program `Main_propres` data for different values of $\vec{\kappa}$ that result in the same value of the eigenvalue $-\rho^2(\vec{\kappa})$ of the Laplacian operator are consolidated. In the program `Main_lobsres` geometrically equivalent data are consolidated over sites, links and plaquette diagonals, as allowed by the intrinsic symmetries of the problem.

This type of consolidation is possible, and further decreases the statistical errors in the data, because these measurements are related by symmetry transformations under which the theory is invariant, and because they are, by and large, statistically independent from one another. In the case of the measurements in momentum space the various measurements which are consolidated are equivalent because the propagator can depend on the modes $\vec{\kappa}$ only through the eigenvalues $-\rho^2(\vec{\kappa})$ of the Laplacian, and not directly on the values of the individual integer coordinates κ_μ . In this case the statistical independence of the various measurements is related to the very fact that the theory is trivial, and hence does not couple different lattice modes, as we can verify a posteriori. In the case of the measurements associated with the local observables, the various measurements which are consolidated are equivalent because they are related to each other by the discrete translation and rotation invariances of the lattice. In this case they are almost completely statistically independent because there is very little correlation between the fields at different sites. In fact, it is possible to show that in the continuum limit the fields $\varphi(\vec{x})$ at two different sites become completely uncorrelated from one another. A simple physical proof of this fact can be found in [6].

The program that runs the longest is `Main_sampler`, specially if the lattice is large and high-precision statistics are required. The numerical work presented in this paper involved approximately 400,000 hours of CPU time on a single 4 GHz processor. This program is prepared to run in parallel on many CPUs or cores of a multiprocessing machine, as well as on many nodes of a parallel machine, such as a cluster of processing nodes. Due to the parallelization the actual wall-clock time for producing the data was reduced to approximately 1500 hours, or about 2 months. Each instance of the program on a given processor writes out sampling data for each one of the observables, with one sample per line in the output data files. All this is done within a well-structured standardized sub-directory tree. There are control files that record the number of processors involved in a particular run and the number of sub-averages already produced for that run, as well as various log files. Once a particular run is done, all the output files, for each one of the various observables, one from each processor, can be concatenated together in a single consolidated output data file, including the contributions from all processors, for that observable. Included in the source code tar file there is a shell script called `collect_parallel_data` that does this.

The Monte Carlo program uses two different algorithms in order to update the field configurations and create a Markovian chain of configurations. The direction of the field values, which in our case here is just their orientations, as given by their signs, is updated by the Wolff cluster algorithm [8], which is the most effective one for this purpose, since it is numerically efficient and essentially eliminates any troublesome auto-correlations along the Markovian chain. In order to update the magnitude of the fields we use the Metropolis algorithm [9], with the lattice set in what is called a checkerboarding configuration, in which we separate the sites into two groups of mutually independent sites, the odd sites and the

even sites, as defined by the parity of the sum of all their d integer coordinates n_μ . In this way we have that every next-neighbor of an even site is an odd site, and vice-versa. This allows us to update one group all at once, while keeping the other group fixed, and hence to avoid giving origin to unwanted correlations within that group, along the Markovian chain. Due to this, and given that we use periodic boundary conditions on the lattice, we are able to use only even values of N , starting at $N = 2$, because otherwise the separation of the sites into two mutually non-interacting groups would be impossible.

Monte Carlo programs can be parallelized in a trivial way, since it is enough to have each independent processor generate independent sub-averages towards a global total average. Each processor can do this in a completely independent fashion, without depending on other processors at all, and will produce statistically independent results so long as the process at each processor uses a different value of the random seed. The seed for the random number generator is chosen and periodically changed, from each sub-average to the next, using the true random number generator `/dev/urandom` of the Linux operating system, that does this by collecting entropy during the operation of the hardware, and thus keeping and using a cache of entropy. The use of this native Linux random number generator is probably the greatest difficulty in porting the programs to other operating systems, in which this system facility may not be available.

The implementation in the program of the Fourier transform and its inverse presents particular challenges. This transform is represented by a very large double-precision real matrix, of dimensions $N^d \times N^d$, with elements involving either exponential functions or sines and cosines. Since the Fourier transformation is executed many times, the repeated calculation of these matrix elements becomes very expensive in terms of processing time. On the other hand, only a relatively small collection of different real numbers appears in these matrix elements, each one being repeated many times along them. The solution adopted was to calculate these real numbers only once, then store the small number of different values of these elements, and use them in the transformation matrix via an indexation system, which maps the integer coordinates of each matrix element to the corresponding double-precision real value. In this way a very large number of dynamical real numbers was traded for a much smaller number of static real numbers, plus the corresponding integers that are the addresses of those real numbers in the transformation matrix. These indexation integers are also static, and can be defined as short (16-bit) integers, further reducing the memory size requirements.

The idea of integer indexation is also used for several other ends in the program, such as making contiguous lists of even and odd sites, contiguous lists of the neighbors of even and odd sites, contiguous lists of the neighbors of arbitrary sites, and contiguous lists of sites, links and plaquette diagonals. The use of such indexation matrices makes the program both more efficient and easier to read, so long as the names of the variables involved are judiciously chosen.

In this program the definition of a single sweep of the lattice, for the acquisition of a single sample, consists of three parts: first a single trial at the Metropolis update of every single even site, then a single trial at the Metropolis update of every single odd site, and finally the construction of a certain number of Wolff clusters, to ensure that every site was tested once, on average, to be flipped as part of a cluster. The samplings were organized in sub-averages of a global average, to enable us to calculate the dispersion of the sub-averages around the total average, and therefore to evaluate the standard statistical errors of the final averages. We used large sub-averages, of 25000 sweeps each, with a total of 1000 such sub-averages. This corresponds to 25×10^6 sweeps in total, and to that same number of samples, thus corresponding to a nominal statistical error level of 1 in 5000, or 0.02%.

It should be noted here that the `Main_sampler` program makes rather extensive use of disk space. Even moderately large lattices can easily produce more than 1 TB of raw data on large statistics runs. When concatenating the various output data files from individual processors into a single global output data file, this disk space requirement will momentarily double. After the calculation of the global averages and of their standard statistical errors by the program `Main_aversig`, in the statistical analysis phase, the raw data can then be deleted, which will radically reduce the disk space requirements for permanent storage of the final results and their standard errors.

7 Numerical Results

The numerical results presented here can be classified as being of two basic types. First we have the results in momentum space, as presented in the development of the theory that was given in Section 4. Then we have the results in position space, based on the local observables defined and discussed in Section 5. The results in momentum space are all based on the fits to the propagator, from which we obtain the residue $R(\alpha, \lambda)$ of the pole of the propagator and the renormalized mass parameter $\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda)$, according on the expression presented in Equation (27). The results obtained in momentum space for the residue $R(\alpha, \lambda)$ are subsequently used in the expressions for the local observables in position space, as shown in Equations (38) through (42). Therefore our first task here is to document the quality of these momentum-space fits. After that, we can report on the behavior of the results in momentum space, and finally on the behavior of the results in position space.

Due to the inevitable space limitations, only a rather limited set of graphs with the numerical results will be shown here. A much more complete set of processed data and formatted graphs is available on the WWW network, and can be obtained by free download from Zenodo [10]. The statistically processed data are available in readable text format, and the formatted data in graph format are available in a couple of readable vector formats, than can be easily viewed, printed and even manipulated. With the use of the free graphics application `xmgrace` (or just `grace`) one can perform many useful operations on the data, such as zooming in, thus blowing the graphs up in order to look at small details.

7.1 Fits to the Propagator

Given the momentum-space propagator as calculated by the stochastic programs, we need to obtain from it the two essential observables, the residue $R(\alpha, \lambda)$ of the pole and the renormalized mass parameter $\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda)$. In the general case the propagator $\tilde{g}_2(\vec{k})$ is defined as the subtracted two-point function in momentum space,

$$\tilde{g}_2(\vec{k}) = \left\langle |\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k})|^2 \right\rangle_N - \left| \langle \tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k}) \rangle_N \right|^2. \quad (43)$$

However, since in our case here, given that we are working on finite lattices without external sources or fixed boundary conditions, we always have for the expectation value of the field at sites $\langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \rangle_N = 0$ for all \vec{n} , which implies at once that $\langle \tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k}) \rangle_N = 0$ for all \vec{k} , we can in fact simply use

$$\tilde{g}_2(\vec{k}) = \left\langle |\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k})|^2 \right\rangle_N. \quad (44)$$

In all cases of interest here this function can be well fitted by the expression of the propagator of the free theory, for all strictly positive values of $\rho^2(\vec{k})$, with modified values of $R(\alpha, \lambda)$, which is just 1 in the free theory, and $\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda)$, which is just the parameter α in the free

theory. Since our objective here is to obtain the values of $R(\alpha, \lambda)$ and $\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda)$ from the numerical data, we consider this function normalized in the form $N^d \tilde{g}_2(\vec{k})$, and then invert it, thus obtaining the function $f(\vec{k})$ in momentum space, representing the inverted and appropriately rescaled propagator,

$$\begin{aligned} f(\vec{k}) &= \frac{1}{N^d \tilde{g}_2(\vec{k})} \\ &= \frac{\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda)}{R(\alpha, \lambda)} + \frac{1}{R(\alpha, \lambda)} \rho^2(\vec{k}) \\ &= a_0(\alpha, \lambda) + a_1(\alpha, \lambda) \rho^2(\vec{k}), \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

where $a_0(\alpha, \lambda)$ and $a_1(\alpha, \lambda)$ are now the two parameters of a linear fit in terms of $\rho^2(\vec{k})$, and where $f(\vec{k})$ may also be written as $f(\rho^2)$. Once $a_0(\alpha, \lambda)$ and $a_1(\alpha, \lambda)$ are determined, the residue of the pole is given by $R(\alpha, \lambda) = 1/a_1(\alpha, \lambda)$ and the renormalized mass parameter is given by $\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda) = a_0(\alpha, \lambda)/a_1(\alpha, \lambda)$. In addition to this, since the functions above depend only on the eigenvalues of the Laplacian $\rho^2(\vec{k})$, and there are several different modes \vec{k} that result in the same value of $\rho^2(\vec{k})$, we can consolidate the values of the function $f(\vec{k}) = f(\rho^2)$ in terms of the values of $\rho^2(\vec{k})$, taking averages and propagating the errors appropriately. This results in a certain number n of independent values of $\rho^2(\vec{k})$, which we will denote by x_i , for $i = 1, \dots, n$. Note that we start the counter i at one, which means that we exclude the zero-mode $\vec{k} = \vec{0}$, with $\rho^2(\vec{k}) = 0$. We therefore have the function in this notation, leaving aside the dependencies on α and λ for the time being,

$$f(x_i) = a_0 + a_1 x_i. \quad (46)$$

The problem of finding R , α_R and their standard errors is thus reduced to the problem of finding a_0 , a_1 and their standard errors. This can be done by the procedure of fitting the numerical data to the linear expression given in Equation (46) above. We therefore have a χ^2 -fit minimization problem, with the n data points $y_i = 1/[N^d \tilde{g}_{2,i}]$ to be compared to the fitting function $f_i = f(x_i)$ at the positions $x_i = \rho_i^2$. Given that the standard errors σ_i associated to the data points y_i can vary significantly with the values of i , we will use the weighted version of the χ^2 function, which is defined as

$$\chi^2(a_0, a_1) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{a_0 + a_1 x_i - y_i}{\sigma_i} \right)^2. \quad (47)$$

It is important to emphasize here that we will use only the range $i = 1, \dots, n$ for the data points, avoiding the value $i = 0$, which is the zero mode, because it gets severely entangled with the symmetry breaking process. The use of these weights can be interpreted in several ways. First, this is a way to give more influence over the overall result of the fitting process to those measurements that have smaller errors and therefore are more precise. Second, this makes the sum defining $\chi^2(a_0, a_1)$ intrinsically dimensionless, regardless of the physical units or nature of the quantities involved. Third, when we consolidate physically equivalent measurements and propagate errors, this automatically uses the fact that a particular value of i refers to the average of several independent measurements, and increases its influence accordingly, since under Gaussian error propagation σ_i^2 decreases linearly with the number of consolidated observations, so that $1/\sigma_i^2$ effectively counts the number of measurements that were consolidated in a particular value of i .

The function $\chi^2(a_0, a_1)$ is a positive function that goes to infinity in every limit to infinity along the (a_0, a_1) plane, in any direction. It is a continuous and differentiable function of both a_0 and a_1 , and therefore has a single point of minimum. The position

of this minimum can be obtained analytically, if we consider the two partial derivatives of $\chi^2(a_0, a_1)$ with respect to a_0 and a_1 ,

$$\frac{\partial \chi^2}{\partial a_0} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{a_0 + a_1 x_i - y_i}{\sigma_i^2}, \quad (48)$$

$$\frac{\partial \chi^2}{\partial a_1} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{a_0 + a_1 x_i - y_i}{\sigma_i^2} x_i. \quad (49)$$

The condition determining the location of the extremal point is that both partial derivatives be zero at the point of minimum, which can be used to determine a_0 and a_1 , resulting in the pair of linear equations

$$a_0 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2} \right) + a_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right), \quad (50)$$

$$a_0 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right) + a_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^2}{\sigma_i^2} \right) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i y_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right), \quad (51)$$

which forms quite a simple linear system of equations for a_0 and a_1 . This can easily be solved for a_0 and a_1 , as follows. Multiplying Equations (50) and (51) by appropriate factors and subtracting these two equations in order to eliminate a_1 we get for a_0 ,

$$a_0 = \frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^2}{\sigma_i^2} \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right) - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i y_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right)}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2} \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^2}{\sigma_i^2} \right) - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right)^2}. \quad (52)$$

All these sums can be calculated numerically in a straightforward manner. Multiplying now the same Equations (50) and (51) by other appropriate factors and subtracting these two equations in order to eliminate a_0 we get for a_1 ,

$$a_1 = \frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2} \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i y_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right) - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right)}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2} \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^2}{\sigma_i^2} \right) - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right)^2}. \quad (53)$$

Again all these sums can be calculated numerically in a straightforward manner. Note that the denominator is the same as in Equation (52), and that it does not depend on the data points y_i . Note also that all the sums are quite simple and follow a regular pattern. There is one sum without x_i or y_i , there are two sums with powers of x_i only, one sum with only y_i and one sum with the product $x_i y_i$, which we denote as

$$\Sigma_{x^0 y^0} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2}, \quad (54)$$

$$\Sigma_{x^1 y^0} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{\sigma_i^2}, \quad (55)$$

$$\Sigma_{x^2 y^0} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^2}{\sigma_i^2}, \quad (56)$$

$$\Sigma_{x^0y^1} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_i}{\sigma_i^2}, \quad (57)$$

$$\Sigma_{x^1y^1} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i y_i}{\sigma_i^2}. \quad (58)$$

In terms of these quantities our results can be written as

$$a_0 = \frac{\Sigma_{x^2y^0}\Sigma_{x^0y^1} - \Sigma_{x^1y^0}\Sigma_{x^1y^1}}{\Sigma_{x^0y^0}\Sigma_{x^2y^0} - \Sigma_{x^1y^0}^2}, \quad (59)$$

$$a_1 = \frac{\Sigma_{x^0y^0}\Sigma_{x^1y^1} - \Sigma_{x^1y^0}\Sigma_{x^0y^1}}{\Sigma_{x^0y^0}\Sigma_{x^2y^0} - \Sigma_{x^1y^0}^2}. \quad (60)$$

There are two types of errors involved in the fitting process. On the one hand there is the overall fitting error, which describes how well the analytical expression used fits the data. On the other hand there is the uncertainty in the values of a_0 and a_1 due to the numerical errors σ_i of y_i . These last ones can be calculated by straightforward propagation of errors. In order to do this we need to calculate the partial derivatives of a_0 and a_1 with respect to y_j . Since y_i does not appear in the denominator of our results in Equations (52) and (53), this calculation is quite simple, and we get

$$\frac{\partial a_0}{\partial y_j} = \frac{1}{\sigma_j^2} \frac{\Sigma_{x^2y^0} - x_j \Sigma_{x^1y^0}}{\Sigma_{x^0y^0}\Sigma_{x^2y^0} - \Sigma_{x^1y^0}^2}, \quad (61)$$

$$\frac{\partial a_1}{\partial y_j} = \frac{1}{\sigma_j^2} \frac{x_j \Sigma_{x^0y^0} - \Sigma_{x^1y^0}}{\Sigma_{x^0y^0}\Sigma_{x^2y^0} - \Sigma_{x^1y^0}^2}. \quad (62)$$

Using the standard formula for the propagation of errors we now get, after some rather remarkable cancellations and simplifications

$$\sigma_{a_0} = \sqrt{\frac{\Sigma_{x^2y^0}}{\Sigma_{x^0y^0}\Sigma_{x^2y^0} - \Sigma_{x^1y^0}^2}}, \quad (63)$$

$$\sigma_{a_1} = \sqrt{\frac{\Sigma_{x^0y^0}}{\Sigma_{x^0y^0}\Sigma_{x^2y^0} - \Sigma_{x^1y^0}^2}}. \quad (64)$$

Therefore, after some lengthy algebraic work we get simple formulas for both the coefficients in Equations (59) and (60), and their errors in Equations (63) and (64), always with the same denominator.

The other type of error, relating to the fit as a whole, can be estimated by comparing areas. If we interpolate the discrete functions f_i and y_i by continuous functions over a range of values of ρ^2 , we can then consider comparing the two areas under the curves of the graphs of these functions, one for the fitting function and another for the data. The area between these two curves, compared to the area under one of them, will tell us how good the fit is. In our discrete environment here what we can do is to look at the differences between the fitting function f_i and the data y_i , over the range $i = 1, \dots, n$,

$$\Delta_i = f_i - y_i, \quad (65)$$

where the fitting function f_i is given in Equation (46). Since we do not want variations with opposite signs to cancel each other, we consider the sum of the squares of these differences, which has the dimensions of squared area,

Global Fitting Errors			
$\Delta A/A$	$d = 3$	$d = 4$	$d = 5$
$N = 2$	3.1389×10^{-4}	3.0615×10^{-4}	2.2366×10^{-4}
$N = 4$	2.1905×10^{-4}	0.9212×10^{-4}	0.4239×10^{-4}
$N = 6$	2.0070×10^{-4}	0.6554×10^{-4}	—————
$N = 8$	2.0195×10^{-4}	0.6779×10^{-4}	—————

Table 1: Average of the global fitting errors, taken over a significant part of the parameter plane. The errors are given by $\Delta A/A$, and these results show that they are compatible with the expected statistical errors of the simulations.

$$(\Delta A)^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta_i^2. \quad (66)$$

Note that this is essentially the definition of the χ^2 function, so that we will actually use the usual weighted definition of this function, for the same reasons as before,

$$(\Delta A)^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\Delta_i}{\sigma_i} \right)^2, \quad (67)$$

which in principle should be divided by the normalization factor

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2}. \quad (68)$$

However, since we are going to compare this quantity to another average of the same type, with the same normalization factor, we may ignore this normalization factor for now. As a reference value for this quantity we compare it to the weighted squared area A^2 under the fitting function, defined in the same way,

$$A^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_i}{\sigma_i} \right)^2, \quad (69)$$

which should also be divided by the normalization factor given in Equation (68). We thus get the ratio representing the quality of the fit,

$$\frac{\Delta A}{A} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\Delta_i}{\sigma_i} \right)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_i}{\sigma_i} \right)^2}}. \quad (70)$$

This number, on a scale given by the interval $[0, 1]$, will give us an idea of how good the fit is, that is, of how well the data is represented by the function used for the fit. The value zero indicates a perfect fit. It is to be expected that this quantity cannot be significantly smaller than the relative statistical errors which are intrinsic to the number of samplings used in the statistics, in our case here 2×10^{-4} , possibly divided by the square root of the number of consolidated entries in each case. In Table 1 one can see the average value of

Fits of the Inverted Propagator

Figure 2: Examples of the fits to the inverted propagator for $d = 4$, $N = 8$, $r = 1.0$, and the angles $\theta = 30^\circ$, $\theta = 60^\circ$ and $\theta = 120^\circ$. The data are represented by the symbols, and the fits are represented by the lines.

$\Delta A/A$, calculated over a significant part of the (r, θ) parameter plane, for each dimension d and for each lattice size N . The global fitting errors are smaller for the larger lattices because in these cases we have a larger number of equivalent data that were consolidated together. As one can see, these overall fitting errors are essentially compatible with the expected statistical fluctuations of the runs, so that the fits are essentially perfect within the statistical expectations.

In Figure 2 we can see three examples of the fit to the inverted propagator in a few typical cases, with $d = 4$, $N = 8$, $r = 1.0$ and three values of θ , with $\theta = 30^\circ$ in the broken-symmetric phase, $\theta = 60^\circ$ near the phase transition, and $\theta = 120^\circ$ in the symmetric phase. In this graph the data points are represented by the symbols and the linear fits are represented by the lines. The behavior of the fitting function and of the data, as well as the quality of the fit, are essentially the same in all other cases. This graph is meant only at giving an illustrative visual idea of the quality of the fits. The fits shown were calculated numerically by the graphics package, instead of by the exact analytical approach described above, and used to construct Table 1. The correlation coefficient of the fit returned by the graphics package was always essentially equal to 1.0, indicating an excellent fit. As one can see, the data error bars are quite small, barely visible in the scale of the graph.

7.2 Results in Momentum Space

The results in momentum space were obtained by scanning the parameter space of the theory, with the use of the coordinates (r, θ) , and then using the techniques described in

Figure 3: An example of the momentum-space propagator, for the case $d = 4$ and $N = 8$, measured over a significant part of the parameter plane.

Subsection 7.1 in order to calculate R and α_R . In Figure 3 we can see the results for the dimensionless renormalized mass parameter α_R obtained from the momentum-space propagator, over a significant part of the parameter plane, for the case $d = 4$, $N = 8$, with $r = 0.1, \dots, 5.0$. For each curve shown the $\theta \rightarrow 0$ limit to the left side is exactly equal to twice the value of the $\theta \rightarrow \pi$ limit to the right side, which corresponds to the free theory, and is itself given by the value of r . All the curves emanate from a point close to the θ axis, which is an approximation of the position of the critical point for these values of d and N . This illustrates how we have $\alpha_R \rightsquigarrow 0$ when we increase N and approach the critical curve in the parameter plane.

In Figure 4 we can see an illustration of the first few steps towards the continuum limit, for the case $d = 4$ and $r = 1.0$, using the range $N = 2, \dots, 8$. Here we can see explicitly that we have $\alpha_R \rightsquigarrow 0$ when we approach the critical point, including when we take the continuum limit. Note that the value of α_R increases to both sides from the position of the critical point. Therefore, although the position of the minimum of α_R can be used as the best evaluation of the position of the critical point, for given values of d and N , α_R is not really an order parameter in the usual sense. Only in theories with continuous symmetry groups, such as the $SO(\mathbb{N})$ theories, there are renormalized mass parameters that can be used as order parameters, due to the Goldstone bosons that exist in those cases, whose masses go to zero in the broken-symmetric phase. As one can see in Figure 4, the continuum limit proceeds very fast with N . This is due to the fact that the proximity to the continuum limit, in terms of the critical behavior of the lattice interpreted as a statistical system, is approximately proportional, not to N , but to the total number N^d of sites in the lattice.

The continuum limit is indeed tied up with the critical behavior of the lattice system.

Illustration of the Continuum Limit

Figure 4: An example of the initial part of the sequence of lattices that constitute the continuum limit, for the case $d = 4$ and $r = 1.0$.

The behavior of the order parameter σ_0^2 defined in Equation (20) can be seen in Figure 5, for the case $d = 4$ and $r = 1.0$. In the continuum limit the order parameter tends to zero in the symmetric phase, to the right of the critical point, and remains different from zero in the broken-symmetric phase, to the left of the critical point. The curves $\sigma_0^2(\theta)$ shown diverge to infinity as $-\alpha/\lambda = \cot(\theta)$ when we make $\theta \rightarrow 0$, independently of the values of N and r . The value of these curves at the smallest value of θ that was used, which was 5° , is approximately given by $\cot(\pi/36) \simeq 11.43$, also independently of the values of N and r . As one can see, the finite-lattice curves approach a limiting curve very fast. Despite the fact that the curves diverge to infinity as we make $\theta \rightarrow 0$, they are still continuous at the critical point, including in the continuum limit. It is apparent, however, that in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit the limiting curve becomes non-differentiable at the critical point.

7.3 Results in Position Space

In Figures 6, 7 and 8 we can see some examples of the results of the various local measurements of the renormalized mass parameter α_R , for the case $d = 4$, $N = 8$ and $r = 1.0$, as well as the comparison of these with the corresponding results from momentum space. In Figure 6 we can see the results α_R from momentum space and $\alpha_{R,s}$ from the local widths of the field at sites, as given in Equations (27) and (38). The match is quite good in the symmetric phase, but the local result detaches from the momentum-space result in the region around the critical point, and simply becomes very close to zero in the broken-symmetric case. It is important to note that this has nothing to do with zero-mass Goldstone bosons, which do not exist in this theory since its symmetry group is discrete and not continuous. This is just the interference of the symmetry breaking mechanism with the analytical results

Figure 5: An example of the initial part of the approach of the order parameter σ_0^2 to the critical behavior, for the case $d = 4$ and $r = 1.0$.

originating from the free theory.

In Figure 7 we can see the results α_R from momentum space, as well as $\alpha_{R,l}$ and $\alpha_{R,\Delta l}$ from the local correlations and squared variations of the field over links, as given in Equations (27), (39) and (41). In the case of the results from the local correlation function over links the behavior is similar to that of the results from the widths at sites. The match is quite good in the symmetric phase, but detaches around the critical point and becomes close to zero in the broken-symmetric phase. In the case of the local squared variations over links the match is remarkably good, and extends to the whole range of values of θ , including throughout the region near the critical point. While the results for the correlation function can be seen to be very slightly below the curve of α_R from momentum space even in the symmetric phase, if we amplify the scales of the graph sufficiently, those for the squared variations over links match the momentum-space results with extraordinary precision. Essentially all the local squared-variation results coincide with the corresponding momentum-space results well within the statistical error bars of either measurement.

In Figure 8 we can see the results α_R from momentum space, as well as $\alpha_{R,d}$ and $\alpha_{R,\Delta d}$ from the local correlations and squared variations of the field over plaquette diagonals, as given in Equations (27), (40) and (42). The situation in this case is completely analogous to that of the corresponding quantities measured over links, with the results from the local correlation functions detaching around the critical point and becoming close to zero in the broken-symmetric phase, and those from the local squared variations matching the momentum-space results extremely well, for all values of θ . The reason why in all these three cases, that is, of the results from the local widths at sites, from the local correlations over links and from the local correlations over diagonals, are always below the momentum-

Figure 6: Comparison of the measurements of α_R and $\alpha_{R,s}$, for the case $d = 4$, $N = 8$ and $r = 1.0$.

space curve, even if only very slightly so in the symmetric phase, is that the symmetry is never fully realized on finite lattices, it is always broken, even if only very slightly. It only becomes an exactly realized symmetry in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit. The observables involving the local squared variations of the field are immune to this effect, since they are invariant under the operation of subtracting from the fields their expectation values.

In order to better document how well the results from the local squared variations over links and plaquette diagonals match the corresponding results from momentum space, we compared the absolute values of differences given by $|\alpha_R - \alpha_{R,\Delta l}|$ and $|\alpha_R - \alpha_{R,\Delta d}|$ with the corresponding statistical errors, propagated from the errors of the observables involved, in order to verify whether or not these differences are statistically compatible with zero. In Tables 2 and 3 we can see these results, showing that they are indeed compatible with zero. Note that all the numbers shown in these tables should be multiplied by 10^{-5} , thus indicating that both the differences and their errors are very small, and quite compatible with the general statistical error level of 2×10^{-4} of our simulations. Therefore, there are no detectable differences between the results from the local squared variations at links or plaquette diagonals and the momentum-space propagator, that can be detected with the available statistics. This suggests rather strongly that these two results from local observables might in fact be exactly equal to the result from the momentum space observable, on every finite N -lattice, as well as in the continuum limit.

The deviation of the results for $\alpha_{R,s}$ associated to the local width of the fields, $\alpha_{R,l}$ associated to the local correlations across links and $\alpha_{R,d}$ associated to the local correlations across plaquette diagonals, from the corresponding results from momentum space, can be understood qualitatively in terms of the symmetry breaking mechanism, and the related

Figure 7: Comparison of the measurements of α_R , $\alpha_{R,l}$ and $\alpha_{R,\Delta l}$, for the case $d = 4$, $N = 8$ and $r = 1.0$, illustrating the quality of the $\alpha_{R,\Delta l}$ measurements.

critical behavior of the lattice system. Taking the case of the local width at sites as an example for this discussion, we recall that the value of $\alpha_{R,s}$ is to be obtained as the solution of Equation (38), when we use in its left-hand side the expectation values obtained in the non-linear theory. We may write this equation, separating the contribution of the zero mode from the rest of the sum, as

$$\langle \varphi^2(\vec{n}) \rangle_N - \langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \rangle_N^2 = \frac{R}{N^d} \frac{1}{\alpha_R} + \frac{R}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k} \neq \vec{0}}^{N^d-1} \frac{1}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R}. \quad (71)$$

If we consider the left-hand side of Equation (71) in the non-linear theory, when the symmetry breaks the value of the field at any typical site, instead of undergoing random fluctuations around zero, starts to undergo those same random fluctuations around a much larger absolute value, due to the fact that the fields tend to align in some arbitrary direction. In our case here this arbitrary direction can be either positive or negative, and from the form of the potential in the broken-symmetric phase and the position of its minima we can see that the absolute value around which the fields now fluctuate is of the order of $\sqrt{-\alpha/\lambda}$. Therefore the value of the observable in the first term of the the left-hand side of Equation (71) is of the order of $-\alpha/\lambda$, which has a positive value in the broken-symmetric phase. This value is typically quite large in the broken-symmetric phase, and goes to infinity as $\theta \rightarrow 0$.

The reason why the left-hand side of Equation (71) has a distorted value is that the second term in that left-hand side is zero due to the drift of the direction of symmetry breaking on finite lattices, which implies that in practice $\langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \rangle_N = 0$, so that the values

Figure 8: Comparison of the measurements of α_R , $\alpha_{R,d}$ and $\alpha_{R,\Delta d}$, for the case $d = 4$, $N = 8$ and $r = 1.0$, illustrating the quality of the $\alpha_{R,\Delta d}$ measurements.

of the quantities to be subtracted are not available for measurement by us. This makes this left-hand side much larger than it should be. If we now consider the right-hand side of Equation (71), we have for the remaining sum seen there

$$\frac{R}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k} \neq \vec{0}}^{N^d-1} \frac{1}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R} < \frac{R}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k}}^{N^d} \frac{1}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R}, \quad (72)$$

where this last sum on the right-hand side is the squared dispersion of values of the field at any arbitrarily given site \vec{n} , in the free theory, which is defined by

$$\sigma^2(N) = \left\langle \varphi^2(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N - \left\langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N^2. \quad (73)$$

On finite lattices $\sigma^2(N)$ is a finite number, or course, and in addition to this, in the cases $d \geq 3$ the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limits of these quantities exist and are finite, of the order of 1, in fact. In the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit they can be obtained with good precision by adding up progressively larger finite sums and extrapolating to $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit [11], while keeping the mass m_R constant, finite and non-zero, and it results that in each dimension $\sigma(\infty)$ is given approximately by

$$\begin{aligned} d = 3 : \quad \sigma(\infty) &\simeq 0.5027, \\ d = 4 : \quad \sigma(\infty) &\simeq 0.3936, \\ d = 5 : \quad \sigma(\infty) &\simeq 0.3400. \end{aligned} \quad (74)$$

It therefore follows that the remaining sum in Equation (71) is a limited quantity, of the order of 1. Therefore, if the left-hand side of Equation (71) is larger than this limit, the

The Differences over Lattice Links and their Errors			
$(\times 10^{-5})$	$d = 3$	$d = 4$	$d = 5$
$N = 2$	3.2749 ± 276.3985	3.3593 ± 206.1028	2.6093 ± 165.5582
$N = 4$	4.4933 ± 59.9650	1.5193 ± 40.7928	0.63092 ± 27.67623
$N = 6$	4.0607 ± 28.9027	1.0104 ± 17.4449	—————
$N = 8$	4.7233 ± 18.2638	1.7913 ± 9.8056	—————

Table 2: Average differences $|\alpha_R - \alpha_{R,\Delta l}|$ and their errors, for the case of links, showing that the differences are compatible with zero. All numbers and errors reported are to be multiplied by 10^{-5} .

The Differences over Plaquette Diagonals and their Errors			
$(\times 10^{-5})$	$d = 3$	$d = 4$	$d = 5$
$N = 2$	16.0923 ± 272.0470	17.1524 ± 202.1565	12.8318 ± 162.4850
$N = 4$	13.9292 ± 57.6704	4.8652 ± 39.4801	1.7012 ± 26.9667
$N = 6$	16.6490 ± 27.5010	4.2428 ± 16.8326	—————
$N = 8$	18.1471 ± 17.3227	4.8290 ± 9.4596	—————

Table 3: Average differences $|\alpha_R - \alpha_{R,\Delta d}|$ and their errors, for the case of plaquette diagonals, showing that the differences are compatible with zero. All numbers and errors reported are to be multiplied by 10^{-5} .

value of the remaining sum cannot match it for any value of α_R . In this case, in order to satisfy the equation, it is necessary to decrease α_R , so that the contribution of the first term on the right-hand side, which is the contribution of the zero mode to the sum, can become large enough to match the anomalously large value on the left-hand side. This is the mechanism through which the numerical resolution of Equation (38) for α_R in such cases drives the value of $\alpha_{R,s}$ towards zero. Similar arguments can be made in the cases of $\alpha_{R,l}$ and $\alpha_{R,d}$, as solutions of Equations (39) and (40), respectively.

In all cases it is the contribution of the zero mode to the sums, and the fact that the information for the appropriate subtractions is not available, that causes all the trouble. In order to avoid this, one way would be to run simulations in the presence of a constant external source j . In this case all the information for the subtractions would become available, so that we would then be able to use any of the local observables developed here in order to get α_R correctly in both phases. This change would shift the values of all the observables, but would still allow us to compare them to one another, and therefore would also allow the use of all the observables given in Equations (38) through (42), for all values of θ , without the large deviations found here in the broken-symmetric phase.

8 Conclusions

We presented in this paper a small set of observables that can be used for the measurement of the renormalized mass m_R , and that do this locally on the lattice, at single sites, single links or single diagonals of plaquettes, using only the measurements obtained at those geometrical elements. In order to define these local observables we used the fact that the theory under examination is known to be trivial. The triviality allows us to express the

relevant expectation values of the non-linear theory using the known expressions that are the exact solutions for the same observables in the free theory. These expressions are exact in the continuum limit, but work very well even on finite lattices.

Extensive numerical tests revealed that these local observables are precise tools for the determination of the dimensionless renormalized mass parameter α_R , and ultimately for the determination of the renormalized mass m_R . It is clear that these local observables can be very useful instruments. In fact, in any case in which we have any reason to introduce into the theory an external source that is dependent on position, and which is more than just an infinitesimal one meant only at the taking of derivatives and subsequent setting to zero, they constitute the only reasonable way to measure the renormalized mass.

As a consequence of their definitions, both the measurements of α_R in momentum space, using the momentum-space propagator, and in position space, using the local observables, are just approximations on finite lattices, that become exact only in the continuum limit. However, we verified that in many cases these approximations are in fact very good, even on very small lattices. One example of this is the high quality of the fits of the measured momentum-space propagator to the form of the propagator of the free theory, which results essentially perfect within statistical errors, even on the smallest possible lattices.

We verified that both the measurements of α_R from the momentum-space propagator, as given in Equation (27), and of $\alpha_{R,\Delta l}$ and $\alpha_{R,\Delta d}$ from the local squared differences of the fields across links and plaquette diagonals, as given in Equations (39) and (40), are insensitive to the zero mode and its distortion caused by the spontaneous symmetry breaking. These three results match each other so well that one is led to surmise that they are exactly equal even on finite lattices. However, the extraordinarily precise match between these results does not mean that any of these results are exact on finite lattices. Instead of this, it probably means that the three observables are measuring exactly the same thing, not only in the continuum limit, as is to be expected, but on finite lattices as well.

In addition to this, even in the case of the values of $\alpha_{R,s}$ obtained from the width at single sites, and the values of $\alpha_{R,l}$ and $\alpha_{R,d}$ obtained from the correlations at single links and at single plaquette diagonals, as defined in Equations (38), (39) and (40) respectively, although they do not match the corresponding values of α_R from momentum space so well, where they do match those results approximately they do so in a way that is clearly not related to the value of N . The mismatches found can be understood completely in terms of the symmetry breaking mechanism and its effect on the zero mode, regardless of the value of N , and independently of the $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit.

One objective of the introduction of the new observables was to allow for the measurement of the renormalized mass independently of the measurement of the propagator in momentum space and hence of the calculation of the Fourier transforms of the field. However, this separation of the position-space measurements from the momentum-space measurement is not complete, due to the dependency of the observables given in Equations from (38) to (42) on the residue R . In order to accomplish this, it will probably be necessary to introduce external sources, so as to eliminate the random drift and thus render the expectation value of the fields available for measurement.

As the technique now stands, we may still perform approximate measurements of m_R locally in position space, using the observables given in Equations from (33) to (37), that is, simply using the approximation that $R = 1$ but, in order to perform more precise measurements, alternative ways to measure the field renormalization constant R must be found. The introduction of the external sources would also be necessary in order to improve the results for the observables $\alpha_{R,s}$, $\alpha_{R,l}$ and $\alpha_{R,d}$ in the broken-symmetric phase. Testing this idea would, of course, require the realization of whole new set of simulations, for

example with the inclusion in the action of a constant external source. The case of the constant external source will be examined in a subsequent paper.

We may conclude that the dynamics of this theory can be described by the statement that the whole physical effect of the non-linear theory is to determine $\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda)$ from the free parameters α and λ , and to generate an expectation value $v_R(\alpha, \lambda)$ of the field, given in terms of the same free parameters. The expectation value $v_R(\alpha, \lambda)$ is related to the first momentum of the statistical distribution, and the renormalized mass parameter $\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda)$ to its second momentum. Only these two momenta are in play in this theory, and no others seem to be relevant. Interestingly, these are exactly the two momenta that are relevant for the role that the scalar field theories play in the standard model of particle physics. But we can go beyond that application, since it is very likely that the results shown here can be extended to the family of scalar field theories with non-linear terms given by $\lambda\varphi^{2p}$, with integer $p > 2$, and possibly to any stable potential $\vartheta(\varphi)$.

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Data Availability Statement

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no experimental datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study. Nevertheless, since the numerical simulation data used in this paper is rather extensive, and took almost half a million hours of CPU time to produce, the whole set of statistically processed data, as well as a fairly complete set of vector-formatted graphs, are available for download from Zenodo [10].

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors hereby certify that there are no actual or potential conflicts of interest of any of the authors in relation to this article.

Funding Declaration

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